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Dual Apprenticeship and Continuous Vocational Training of German Family Businesses in Central and Eastern Europe: Commitment, Motives and Trends

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Abstract

The VET efforts of large family business in Germany on the one hand, and the risk of the shortage of skilled workers for internationally active German businesses on the other, this paper looks at the involvement of German family businesses in vocational education and training in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE). More specifically, it explores the potential and opportunities of initial and continuing vocational education and training in Central and Eastern European countries of major significance to the German economy, sets out the obstacles that exist and examines where action is needed. The study focuses on industrial and technical occupations, since a significant portion of German family businesses in CEE are industrial companies with a particular need for personnel in this field.

The economic importance of Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) to Germany and German businesses can be seen, for example, from figures on trade intensity or the ranking of trading partners in foreign trade. Germany's imports from Poland (ranked 4th), for instance, today exceed those from Italy (5th) or France (6th). Our analysis includes seven countries: Poland, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania, Bulgaria, Slovakia and Serbia. Between them, these countries are home to no fewer than 4,442 branches of German businesses, employing over 1.4 million people. This indicates the considerable potential for German businesses in the region.

The potential, opportunities, obstacles and the need for action that we have identified in this study result from the particular local contexts in Central and Eastern European countries – contexts that differ considerably from country to country. While a high degree of similarity between the countries might initially be assumed, a closer examination reveals major national differences in the existing environments for vocational education and training. It was therefore necessary to begin by looking at each country's education and training system.

Keywords

Central and Eastern Europe, apprenticeships, German companies

1 Problem definition and research question

The training and continuing education of their own employees has a long tradition in German family businesses. Today, family businesses provide more than 60 percent of all jobs in Germany, 80 percent of training positions (Langenscheidt & May 2020, p. 12) and more than 70 percent of family businesses are active in the area of continuing education (Stiftung Familienunternehmen, 2022a). The interest in training and continuing education will not weaken in the future, but rather continue to strengthen: For 95 percent of next-generation family entrepreneurs (NextGens), employee training and development is a top priority (PwC, 2020).

Due to the great importance of family businesses for Germany as a business location, we will focus below on this particular form of enterprise. To distinguish between family businesses and non-family businesses, we use the definition of the European Commission (European Commission, 2009). Due to their economic importance, family businesses shape the image of the German economy abroad. By way of illustration, the five largest German family businesses are (1) Volkswagen AG, (2) Robert Bosch GmbH, (3) Schwarz Gruppe (Lidl, Kaufland), (4) Fresenius Gruppe and (5) Continental AG (Die Deutsche Wirtschaft, 2022).

The involvement of German companies abroad has already been the subject of several studies in order to capture the phenomenon of the transfer of vocational training at the meso level in the corporate context. For example, studies are available from the United States (Gessler, 2017), South Africa (Peters, 2019), and China, Mexico, and India (Pilz & Wiemann, 2021). The generally existing training engagement of German companies abroad is furthermore of interest, because although the engagement is local, it can have the potential of a systemic effect at regional and national level (Wiemann & Fuchs, 2018).

It is striking that there are no studies on the training activities of German companies in Central and Eastern Europe, even though these countries are of great economic importance for Germany (DeStatis, 2022): Poland, for example, follows directly behind the USA in terms of imports with rank 4 and exports to the Czech Republic (rank 11) are higher than exports to, for example, Korea (rank 18), Japan (rank 20), Mexico (rank 22), India (rank 23) and South Africa (rank 31).

Our study shows what contribution major German family businesses are already making to dual training and continuing vocational training in selected countries in Central and Eastern Europe (CEE) and what opportunities as well as obstacles and resulting need for action exist to improve training and continuing vocational training locally. The study focuses on countries that are of great importance to the German export industry: Poland, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Bulgaria and Serbia. A particular focus is on industrial-technical training occupations.

2 Method

The study opens with country analyses based on documentary research. Seven countries were selected for the study: Poland, the Czech Republic, Hungary, Romania, Slovakia, Bulgaria and Serbia (the choice of countries is explained in the next sub-chapter). The country studies were conducted using documentary research, interviews and the involvement of national experts.

Table 1
Data sample

Country	Employees	up to 249	250 or more	Total
Bulgaria		9	11	20
Poland		0	45	45
Romania		5	23	28
Serbia		0	23	23
Slovakia		0	19	19
Czech Republic		0	33	33
Hungary		0	25	25
Total		14	179	193

Source: Company survey by the Institute of Technology and Education, University of Bremen.

Next, the report looks at the extent to which German family businesses are involved in vocational education and training in the seven countries. Although companies were widely presumed to have such involvement, there were no pre-existing studies of this for Central and Eastern Europe. This is surprising when we consider that the training efforts of German companies outside Europe have been analysed in depth, for instance in the USA, South Africa, China, Mexico and India (Gessler, 2017b; Peters, 2019; Pilz & Wiemann, 2021). The next step, which forms the second part of this study, was therefore an empirical survey of German family businesses (n=193). The data sample is shown in the table 1.

We used this survey to explore the structures of companies' involvement in vocational education and training. The final part of the picture was an impression of what this looks like on the ground. We therefore prepared case studies examining concrete implementation and the considerable work being done by German family businesses in their branches in Central and Eastern Europe. Though not representative, case studies are the method of choice when it comes to capturing a complex issue in a complex, real-life environment as they enable a qualitative rather than quantitative analysis. We use them here to explore the involvement of branches of various German family businesses in Central and Eastern Europe, looking at their training efforts in Poland (Gühring), the Czech Republic (Mubea) and Hungary (Festo) as well as at a partnership between German companies in Romania (including the family businesses Dräxlmaier and Schaeffler). The case studies are based on eight guided interviews with representatives of schools and companies.

Building on the findings of the country analyses, the empirical survey and the case studies, the final section of the study identifies where action is needed. Where is there room for improvement? What political support should be provided from the EU, from government and administration in the countries themselves and from Germany? What action recommendations can be offered to family businesses?

3 Findings

In Germany, German family businesses benefit from the dual training system, which enables companies to align training with operational needs and to qualify skilled workers who fit the company both professionally and socially. Skilled workers form the backbone of the German economy. Today, the growing shortage of skilled workers in Germany (Stiftung Familienunternehmen, 2022a) is jeopardizing the business and operating model based on this and ultimately the future viability of German family businesses.

In Central and Eastern Europe, the situation is even more explosive: On the one hand, there is also a massive shortage of skilled workers. On the other hand, the training of skilled workers does not solve the shortage, but rather exacerbates the problem: Vocational training in Central and Eastern Europe is generally the responsibility of the schools and is detached from the needs of the companies. Practical skills are taught in poorly equipped school workshops. Teachers are generally paid less than people with comparable qualifications on the labor market and, for the most part, do not have the practical work experience, training and equipment to be able to close the gap to the world of work in terms of subject didactics. Against this background, it is not surprising that vocational training in Central and Eastern Europe has a poor image among large sections of the population. The lack of quality and attractiveness, in turn, result in high-achieving students migrating to general education and then to higher education, which further exacerbates the shortage of skilled workers.

This trend is being countered by political reforms: For example, dual apprenticeship options were enshrined in law in six of the seven focused countries: Hungary (2011), Bulgaria (2015), Slovakia (2015), Poland (2016), Romania (2016) and Serbia (2017). These positive developments are supported by a European policy that has been promoting the apprenticeship concept for a decade, by the existing political will for reform on the ground (Tütlys et al., 2022) and by the commitment of the companies providing training, among which the German family businesses occupy a particularly prominent position: 73.6 percent of the family businesses surveyed are currently already providing training in Central and Eastern Europe. According to the companies, this figure is expected to rise to 89 percent in the next two years. Major German family businesses are therefore far more committed to training in Central and Eastern Europe than the national average (around 30 to 40 percent). Another positive aspect is that 74.1 percent of family businesses are promoting local training because they want to assume social responsibility.

Businesses expect a considerable increase in all areas of training over the next five years and see the greatest growth potential in continuing vocational education and training. 40.4 percent of the businesses surveyed expect a considerable increase here, while another 30.6 percent anticipate slight growth. Overall, this means that 71 percent of companies expect to expand their provision of continuing vocational education and training.

Figure 1
Trends

The reasons cited by companies for providing their own VET are the shortage of skilled workers on the labour market (89.6 percent) and other business reasons (e.g. avoiding unsuccessful hires) on the one hand, and a desire to take on social responsibility (74.1 percent) on the other.

The problem of meeting the existing demand for skilled workers is being further exacerbated by companies' growth and the increasing range of work they are doing in CEE (71.5 percent). Despite companies' urgent need for labour, the vast majority of businesses surveyed (81.9 percent) believe that employing people with an academic educational background is no substitute for vocational education and training. Another reason for training people locally is to reduce the need for specialist staff from Germany (including expats).

Figure 2
Reasons for providing own local VET

In addition to these push factors, one in three of the businesses surveyed cited the positive experience of other companies (35.7 percent) and the support offered by the German Chambers of Commerce Abroad (32.1 percent).

4 Conclusion

Our recommendations based on our analysis touch upon three levels: The micro level, comprising actual teaching and learning processes and interactions between stakeholders (including trainees, teachers and instructors); the meso level, i.e. the level of institutions

(companies, schools, school authorities) and institutional actions and collaboration; and the macro (policy) level, which provides the framework determining the responsibilities, opportunities for collaboration and room for manoeuvre of stakeholders and institutions in the VET system. We provide a total of nine action recommendations: three at the micro level, three at the meso level, two at the macro level and one affecting all levels. All the recommendations are aimed at further improving the environment for vocational education and training in Europe (for further information about the recommendations and the conducted study: Stiftung Familienunternehmen, 2022b).

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